

The proposed method has been applied to the determination of bismuth in a number of materials and the results are presented in Table 1. Two standard reference samples MP-1a and MP-2 (CANMET) have also been analysed for bismuth by this method and the results have been compared with the reported values. Precision studies by replicate analysis of one granite sample (B-26) also gave satisfactory results (RSD-6.5%). Recovery has also been checked by standard addition method.

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Zinc with Diphenylcarbazone in Presence of Pyridine

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DIPHENYLCARBAZONE has long been known as a reagent for the detection and determination of a number of metals¹⁻³. It forms chelate complexes with many heavy metals^{4,5}. Zinc(II) forms a purple coloured 1 : 2 complex⁶ with it, but the complex is not easily extractable. In the present investigation it is found that in presence of pyridine, zinc(II) forms with diphenylcarbazone a purple coloured complex which is completely extractable into methyl isobutyl ketone. This forms the basis of the present method which has proved to be very simple and sensitive.

Experimental

A Hilger-UVISPEK spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used for absorbance measurements, pH values were determined with a Elico LI-10 pH-meter.

A stock solution of zinc was prepared from zinc metal (AnalaR) and was standardised by complexometric method⁶. The solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. A 0.3% solution of

diphenylcarbazone was prepared in absolute ethanol. A 5% pyridine solution in distilled water was used. Solutions of 0.2 M boric acid, 0.2 M potassium chloride and 0.2 M sodium hydroxide were prepared to constitute the required buffer. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their chloride, nitrate or sulphate or from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the test solution containing 0.1 to 10 μg of zinc, 5% pyridine (2 ml) and buffer solution (2 ml) were added and the total volume was made upto 10 ml so that pH of the aqueous phase was around 10.0. To it, solutions of 0.3% diphenylcarbazone (1 ml) and MIBK (10 ml) were added and the resulting mixture was shaken for 5 min. The organic layer was separated and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 520 nm against the reagent blank. The zinc content was computed from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The purple coloured zinc(II)–diphenylcarbazone–pyridine complex system extractable into MIBK, exhibits maximum absorbance at 520 nm when measured against the reagent blank and obeys Beer's law over the range 0.01–1 ppm of Zn^{2+} . The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is 0.00078 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity $8.37 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 520 nm. It was found that 0.3% diphenylcarbazone (1 ml) and 5% pyridine (2 ml) were adequate for complete extraction of zinc (0.1–10 μg) in the pH range 9.0–10.0 by a single extraction with 10 ml of MIBK. A 0.2–1% diphenylcarbazone and a 1–15% pyridine can be used without any adverse effect to absorbance value. The extracted species exhibited constant and maximum absorption when pH of the aqueous phase was maintained in the pH range 9.0–10.0. Various solvents such as 1,2-dichloroethane, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, toluene, amyl alcohol and MIBK were tested for extraction of zinc complex, but MIBK was found to be the most effective one. With 10 ml of MIBK, the complex is recovered to the extent of 99.8% by a single extraction. The complex is stable for more than 24 h in MIBK. For complete extraction of the complex, 5 min shaking period was adequate. The absorbance of the complex is independent of temperature in the range 12–35°. Job's method of continuous variation⁷ and mole-ratio method⁸ indicated that a 1 : 2 complex between zinc and diphenylcarbazone is formed. The complex seems to have been stabilised by mixed ligation with pyridine.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of different foreign ions in the determination of zinc (5 μg) was studied. The tolerance limit was set at the amount required to cause less than 3% error in the recovery of zinc. Estimation of zinc in presence of Cu^{2+} was done using thiourea as

masking agent. In presence of Hg^{2+} and Pd^{2+} , iodide solution was used for masking, and in presence of Al^{3+} and Mn^{2+} , solutions of fluoride and citrate respectively were used. Nickel if present must be removed by extraction in chloroform as nickeldimethylglyoximate prior to the estimation of zinc. The following foreign ions (I) caused no interference at I-Zn weight ratio: As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Au^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} and $V^{5+} > 200$; Pt^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and $Mn^{2+} \leq 100$; Zr^{4+} and $Bi^{3+} < 10$; $Mg^{2+} < 50$; Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and $Sn^{2+} < 5$; thio-sulphate, thiourea, fluoride, iodide, thiocyanate, citrate, oxalate, sulphate, phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, dichromate and sulphite ≥ 2000 ; bromide and tartrate < 50 . However, Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , CN^- and EDTA when present even in a very small amount interfere seriously.

TABLE 1 - DETERMINATION OF ZINC IN STANDARD SAMPLES*

Sample no. (Composition)	Zinc found %
Lead concentrates (42G) (Zn, 3.40; Cu, 0.14; Fe, 1.35; Pb, 75.6; S, 14.2; As, 0.32; Mn, 3.21; Sb, 0.15; Bi, 0.02; Ag, 0.074; Au, 0.016 %)	3.31
Gun-metal (6g) (Cu, 86.4; Zn, 1.30; Sn, 10.5; Pb, 1.02; Fe, 0.2; Ni, 0.26; P, 11 %)	1.34

*Obtained from B. A. S. Ltd., U. K.

Applications: The method was applied to determine zinc from standard samples. Dissolution of the samples was done following the standard procedure⁹. The results obtained from three determinations of each sample, are given in Table 1.

Precision and accuracy: A standard solution containing 5 μ g of zinc was estimated (10 times) by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.641 with a standard deviation of 0.007 absorbance unit and a relative error of $\pm 0.78\%$.

The present method is more sensitive than the dithizone method¹⁰ and the determination of zinc can be carried out in presence of most of the common ions. The total operation time in each run is 15-20 min.

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Chlorohydantoin as a New Oxidimetric Titrant in Aqueous Medium

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IN continuation of our earlier work on halo-hydantoin as oxidimetric titrants¹⁻⁵, we introduce the sodium salt of 1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin (which can be called 'chlorohydantoin') as a new oxidimetric titrant in aqueous medium. The results of determination of 22 reductants of diverse types using chlorohydantoin as the titrant are reported.

Experimental

Chlorohydantoin was prepared from dichlorohydantoin (DCH), which in turn, was prepared from 5,5-dimethylhydantoin as reported^{1,6}. DCH (5g) was added in small portions with stirring, to a hot 10% aqueous solution ($\sim 80^\circ$) of sodium hydroxide. When all the DCH dissolved, the solution was cooled in ice to get white crystals of chlorohydantoin, which were washed with ice-cold saturated solution of sodium chloride and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 . The purity of the sample was checked by elemental analysis⁷ (Found: N, 15.6; Cl, 19.0. Requires: N 15.2; Cl, 19.2%). A 0.05M solution of chlorohydantoin was prepared in water. The solution was kept in an amber coloured bottle, and standardised daily iodometrically⁸.

Standard solutions ($\sim 0.1N$) of all reductants other than the two thiosemicarbazide complexes were prepared by the reported methods⁹. The two thiosemicarbazides of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} were prepared by the reported method⁷. Decinormal solutions of these complexes were prepared in 2N hydrochloric acid and the strengths checked by standard methods^{9,10}.

Procedures: For direct visual titration, a 1% solution of solid potassium iodide and 1% starch solution